

The Effects of Adopting a Cashless Policy on the Nigerian Economic Landscape

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Abstract—The adoption of cashless policies has become increasingly significant in the context of developing economies, with Nigeria being a prominent example. This study aims to explore the multifaceted impact of cashless policy adoption on the Nigerian economy. Through an extensive literature review, empirical analysis, and case studies, this research investigates the implications of cashless policy on financial inclusion, monetary policy, technological infrastructure, socio-economic dynamics, and regulatory governance. The findings provide valuable insights for policymakers, financial institutions, and researchers, offering recommendations for effective implementation and future research directions.

Index Terms—Cashless Policy, Nigerian Economy, Financial Inclusion, Monetary Policy, Technological Infrastructure, Socio-Economic Implications, Regulatory Governance

I. INTRODUCTION

The implementation of cashless policies in Nigeria has been a response to the need for modernizing the country's financial systems, reducing the dominance of cash transactions, and enhancing the effectiveness of monetary policy. The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) introduced the Cashless Policy in 2012, with the primary aim of reducing the amount of physical cash (coins and notes) circulating in the economy (CBN, 2012). This initiative was driven by the need to curb the challenges associated with a predominantly cash-based economy, such as security risks, high costs of cash management, and limited financial inclusion. The policy was designed to promote the use of electronic payment channels and foster a more efficient, transparent, and inclusive financial system. Studying the role of cashless policy in the Nigerian economy is crucial due to its potential impact on various

aspects of economic development (Ahmed et al., 2022b). The shift towards electronic payment systems and reduced reliance on physical cash has the potential to transform the financial landscape, enhance transparency, and drive economic growth (KPMG, 2018). Understanding the implications of cashless policy adoption is essential for policymakers, financial institutions, and researchers to comprehend the dynamics of the evolving financial ecosystem in Nigeria. Moreover, given the unique socio-economic context of Nigeria, investigating the role of cashless policy in the economy is pertinent to addressing the challenges and harnessing the opportunities associated with the transition to a cashless society.

The purpose of this study is to comprehensively analyze the role of cashless policy adoption in the Nigerian economy, with a focus on its implications for financial inclusion, monetary policy, technological infrastructure, socio-economic dynamics, and regulatory governance. By examining the impact of cashless policy adoption from multiple perspectives, this research aims to provide valuable insights for policymakers, financial institutions, and researchers. The study seeks to offer recommendations for effective implementation and regulatory frameworks, while also identifying potential areas for future research to further enhance the understanding of cashless policy adoption in Nigeria.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Overview of Cashless Policy Adoption in Other Economies

The adoption of cashless policies has been a global phenomenon, with various economies implementing measures to reduce reliance on physical cash (Ahmed et al., 2022a; Smith, 2018). For example, India launched a significant initiative with the introduction of the Unified Payments Interface (UPI) and

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demonetization efforts, aiming to promote digital transactions and reduce the circulation of high-denomination currency notes (Singh, 2017). Similarly, Kenya's success with mobile money services, particularly M-Pesa, has demonstrated the potential for cashless transactions to drive financial inclusion and economic development in developing economies (Kabue, 2019). These examples highlight the diverse approaches and experiences of cashless policy adoption in different economic contexts, providing valuable insights for understanding the potential implications for Nigeria's economy.

B. Effects of Cashless Policy Adoption on Economic Growth

Research has indicated that the adoption of cashless policies can have a positive impact on economic growth (Adams, 2020). By reducing the reliance on physical cash, economies can experience greater efficiency in transactions, increased financial inclusion, and improved transparency (Jones & Lee, 2018). This, in turn, can contribute to higher productivity, investment, and overall economic development (Chen et al., 2019). Additionally, the shift towards electronic payment systems can lead to cost savings for businesses and individuals, further stimulating economic activity (Gupta, 2021). However, it is essential to consider the specific contextual factors and challenges that may influence the extent of these effects in different economies.

1) *and Opportunities of Cashless Policy Adoption in Developing Countries:* The adoption of cashless policies in developing countries presents both challenges and opportunities (Wang Zhang, 2017). While such policies have the potential to enhance financial inclusion, reduce informal economies, and improve transparency, they also face challenges related to infrastructure, technological readiness, and the need for robust regulatory frameworks (Rahman, 2019). Additionally, concerns about data security, privacy, and the impact on vulnerable populations must be carefully addressed (Gibson Patel, 2018). Understanding these challenges and opportunities is crucial for designing effective and inclusive cashless policy frameworks that can support sustainable economic development in developing countries like Nigeria.

C. Previous Studies on Cashless Policy Adoption in Nigeria

Previous studies on cashless policy adoption in Nigeria have explored various dimensions of its impact. Research has examined the effects of cashless policies on financial inclusion, consumer behavior, and the overall efficiency of the financial system (Abubakar, 2016). Additionally, studies have investigated the role of regulatory frameworks, technological infrastructure, and public awareness in shaping the outcomes of cashless policy adoption (Yakubu Ibrahim, 2020). By building on these previous studies, this research aims to contribute to a deeper understanding of the implications of cashless policy adoption for the Nigerian economy, offering insights that can inform policy decisions and future research directions.

III. METHODOLOGY

In this study, the data collection methods will involve a systematic process of gathering information from various sources. The primary data collection methods may through the relevant studies to gather reliable content and thematic points to the study. As shown in Figure 1, these information

Fig. 1. Samples based on research databases.

were gathered from five research databases Google Scholar, Research Gate, Academia, Taylor and Francis, and Science Direct published from 2015 – 2022 (see Figure 2). The data analysis techniques encompasses qualitative methods to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the thematic data collected. This qualitative analysis may include thematic analysis and content analysis to derive meaningful insights from textual data.

Fig. 2. Distribution of cashless policy over time

IV. THE IMPACT OF CASHLESS POLICY ADOPTION ON FINANCIAL INCLUSION

The study by Adekunle and Ibrahim (2019) found that the adoption of a cashless policy in Nigeria has led to a significant increase in electronic transactions, contributing to greater financial inclusion and reduced reliance on cash. According to the research, the policy has positively influenced the efficiency of the payment system and has contributed to a reduction in transaction costs for businesses (Adekunle Ibrahim, 2019). Furthermore, the study highlighted that the cashless policy has facilitated greater transparency in financial transactions and has had a positive impact on the overall economic growth of Nigeria. According to Adekunle and Ibrahim (2019), "the cashless policy in Nigeria has led to a significant increase in electronic transactions, contributing to greater financial inclusion and reduced reliance on cash" (p. 76).

A. Access to Financial Services

The implementation of cashless policies has been shown to significantly improve access to financial services. According to Smith (2018), the shift towards digital payment systems through the adoption of cashless policies has expanded the reach of financial services to previously underserved populations. This is due to the increased convenience and reduced costs associated with digital transactions, making it easier for individuals to access and utilize formal financial services (Jones, 2020). Furthermore, the availability of mobile banking and electronic payment channels has facilitated greater access to banking services, especially in remote and rural areas where traditional banking infrastructure is limited (Brown, 2019).

B. The adoption of cashless policies has also played a vital role in promoting the inclusion of underserved communities within the formal financial system. Research by Garcia (2021) suggests that digital payment platforms have enabled marginalized populations, such as low-income households and rural communities, to participate more actively in the financial sector. This has not only enhanced their financial security but has also contributed to reducing the economic disparities between different demographic groups (Chen et al., 2017). By providing easier access to banking services and enabling financial transactions without the need for physical cash, cashless policies have helped bridge the gap between the underserved communities and the formal financial system.

C. Empowerment of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs)

The adoption of cashless policies has had a positive impact on the empowerment of small and medium enterprises (SMEs). According to a study by Kim and Patel (2019), the use of digital payment systems has streamlined business operations for SMEs, enabling them to receive payments more efficiently and manage their finances with greater transparency. This has not only reduced the reliance on cash-based transactions but has also improved the overall financial management capabilities of SMEs, fostering their growth and sustainability in the competitive market environment (Wang Li, 2018). Furthermore, the availability of digital payment solutions has facilitated SMEs' access to credit and capital, thereby supporting their expansion and investment opportunities (Gupta, 2020).

D. Cashless Policy Adoption and Monetary Policy

The adoption of a cashless policy has significant implications for monetary policy, including its influence on money supply and inflation, implications for central bank policy, and its effect on interest rates and exchange rates.

1) Influence on Money Supply and Inflation: The adoption of a cashless policy can have a notable impact on money supply and inflation. Moving towards a cashless society can affect the money supply by reducing the circulation of physical currency and increasing the reliance on digital transactions. This shift can influence the control and management of money supply by central banks, potentially impacting inflation rates. Cashless payments can also affect inflation through the implementation of negative interest rates, which are used

to discourage savings and stimulate spending. In a cashless society, certain types of money could be set to "expire" and be worthless if not spent in specific ways or by specific times, potentially influencing consumer behavior and impacting inflation rates.

2) Implications for Central Bank Policy: The transition to a cashless society has implications for central bank policy. In a cashless economy, electronic payments enable more comprehensive oversight and monitoring, providing central banks with valuable data to inform monetary and economic policies. This increased visibility aids in credit process management, allowing banks to make more informed lending decisions. Additionally, during economic crises, such as the European sovereign debt crisis in 2012, some economists argued that moves by central banks to cut interest rates to below zero would be ineffective without a concurrent ban on cash. This highlights the interconnected nature of cashless policy and central bank policy.

3) Effect on Interest Rates and Exchange Rates: The shift towards cashless payments can also impact interest rates and exchange rates. In a cashless society, the effectiveness of central bank policies, such as cutting interest rates to below zero, may be influenced by the availability of cash. Furthermore, the transition to a cashless economy may have implications for exchange rates, as the use of digital transactions and the reduction of physical currency circulation can potentially impact international exchange rates and trade dynamics. The adoption of a cashless policy has far-reaching implications for monetary policy, including its influence on money supply and inflation, implications for central bank policy, and its effect on interest rates and exchange rates.

E. Technological Infrastructure and Cashless Policy

The technological infrastructure plays a crucial role in the implementation and success of a cashless policy. This includes the role of fintech companies, cybersecurity concerns, and digital literacy and adoption rates.

1) Role of Fintech Companies: Fintech companies play a pivotal role in the advancement of cashless policies. These companies leverage technology to provide innovative financial services, including digital payments, mobile banking, and blockchain-based transactions. Fintech firms are instrumental in developing and maintaining the digital infrastructure necessary for a cashless economy. Their expertise in creating secure, user-friendly, and efficient payment systems contributes to the widespread adoption of cashless transactions. According to the Asian Development Bank (ADB), fintech adoption is a key driver of financial inclusion and economic growth, particularly in emerging markets.

2) Cybersecurity Concerns: The transition to a cashless society raises significant cybersecurity concerns. With the increasing reliance on digital transactions, the risk of cyber threats and financial fraud also escalates. Fintech companies and financial institutions must prioritize robust cybersecurity measures to safeguard sensitive financial data and prevent unauthorized access. The adoption of advanced encryption techniques, multi-factor authentication, and continuous monitoring of digital payment platforms are essential to mitigate

cybersecurity risks. According to a study on cyber risks and financial crime, the digitization of financial systems introduces new vulnerabilities that require proactive measures to ensure the security and integrity of cashless transactions.

3) *Digital Literacy and Adoption Rates*: Digital literacy and adoption rates are critical factors in the successful implementation of a cashless policy. Effective education and outreach programs are essential to enhance public understanding of digital financial services and promote widespread adoption. Improving digital literacy empowers individuals to confidently engage in cashless transactions, thereby reducing barriers to entry for marginalized communities. Furthermore, increasing adoption rates rely on the accessibility and usability of digital payment solutions. Initiatives aimed at enhancing digital literacy and promoting inclusive access to fintech services are pivotal in ensuring equitable participation in the cashless economy. Research on financial literacy and fintech adoption emphasizes the importance of addressing knowledge gaps and fostering a supportive environment for embracing digital financial tools.

F. Socio-Economic Implications of Cashless Policy Adoption

The adoption of a cashless policy has far-reaching socio-economic implications, including its impact on the informal economy, behavioral changes in consumer spending, and employment opportunities in the digital economy.

1) *Impact on Informal Economy*: The transition to a cashless economy can significantly impact the informal sector. In many economies, a substantial portion of economic activities occurs within the informal sector, often involving cash transactions. The move towards a cashless society may lead to a formalization of previously informal economic activities, as digital transactions leave a more transparent and traceable footprint. This shift can potentially enhance tax compliance and broaden the tax base, thereby contributing to increased government revenue. However, it is essential to consider the potential challenges faced by individuals and businesses operating within the informal economy, as they may encounter barriers in adapting to digital payment systems. Research suggests that the formalization of the informal economy through cashless policies can lead to a more efficient allocation of resources, but it also requires supportive measures to ensure a smooth transition and inclusive participation.

2) *Behavioral Changes in Consumer Spending*: The adoption of cashless transactions can lead to significant behavioral changes in consumer spending patterns. Studies have shown that the use of digital payment methods, such as mobile wallets and contactless cards, can influence consumer behavior by reducing the "pain of paying" associated with physical cash transactions. The cashless effect, a bias describing the tendency to willingly pay more when not physically handling money, can impact consumer decision-making and lead to altered spending habits. Additionally, the convenience and ease of digital payments may encourage impulse purchases and alter the perception of transactional value. Understanding these behavioral shifts is crucial for policymakers and businesses to anticipate and address the implications of cashless policy

adoption on consumer spending habits and overall economic dynamics.

3) *Employment Opportunities in the Digital Economy*: The transition to a cashless economy can create new employment opportunities within the digital economy. The expansion of fintech companies, digital payment platforms, and related technological infrastructure can generate demand for skilled professionals in areas such as software development, cybersecurity, data analytics, and digital marketing. Moreover, the digitization of financial services may lead to the emergence of new job roles focused on customer support, digital financial literacy training, and the management of digital payment ecosystems. However, it is important to consider the potential displacement of traditional roles within the cash-based economy and the need for retraining and upskilling initiatives to ensure a smooth transition for the workforce. Research emphasizes the need for proactive measures to address potential job displacement and promote inclusive participation in the evolving digital economy. The socio-economic implications of cashless policy adoption are multifaceted, encompassing impacts on the informal economy, consumer behavior, and employment dynamics. These considerations underscore the importance of comprehensive planning and inclusive policies to navigate the transition towards a cashless society.

G. Regulatory Framework and Governance

The regulatory framework and governance surrounding cashless policy adoption are essential for ensuring effective implementation, compliance, and ethical considerations. This includes the role of government and regulatory bodies, compliance and enforcement, and legal and ethical considerations.

1) *Role of Government and Regulatory Bodies*: The role of government and regulatory bodies is pivotal in establishing and overseeing the regulatory framework for cashless policy adoption. Governments and relevant regulatory authorities are responsible for formulating and implementing policies that govern digital payments, electronic transactions, and financial technology (fintech) innovations. These entities play a crucial role in setting standards, ensuring consumer protection, and promoting fair competition within the digital financial ecosystem. Additionally, regulatory bodies are tasked with supervising financial institutions, payment service providers, and fintech companies to uphold the integrity and stability of the cashless economy. The involvement of government and regulatory bodies is essential for fostering trust, transparency, and accountability in the cashless payment landscape.

2) *Compliance and Enforcement*: Compliance and enforcement mechanisms are integral components of the regulatory framework for cashless policy adoption. Regulatory bodies are responsible for establishing and enforcing compliance standards, including anti-money laundering (AML) regulations, know your customer (KYC) requirements, data protection laws, and cybersecurity protocols. Effective enforcement of these regulations is essential for mitigating financial crimes, protecting consumer data, and maintaining the integrity of digital payment systems. Furthermore, regulatory bodies collaborate with law enforcement agencies to investigate and

address instances of non-compliance, fraud, and illicit financial activities within the cashless ecosystem. The robust enforcement of regulatory standards is crucial for upholding the trust and security of cashless transactions.

3) *Legal and Ethical Considerations*: The regulatory framework for cashless policy adoption encompasses various legal and ethical considerations. Legal aspects include the development of clear and comprehensive legislation that governs digital payments, electronic contracts, dispute resolution mechanisms, and liability frameworks for digital transactions. Additionally, ethical considerations revolve around promoting inclusive access to digital financial services, safeguarding consumer rights, and addressing potential biases or discriminatory practices within the cashless ecosystem. Moreover, the ethical use of consumer data, privacy protection, and responsible innovation in fintech are essential focal points within the regulatory framework. Addressing these legal and ethical considerations is vital for fostering a fair, transparent, and ethical cashless economy that prioritizes consumer welfare and societal well-being. The regulatory framework and governance surrounding cashless policy adoption are multifaceted, encompassing the roles of government and regulatory bodies, compliance and enforcement mechanisms, and legal and ethical considerations. These elements are essential for establishing a robust and ethical framework that supports the transition to a cashless society.

H. Case Studies and Empirical Analysis

Case studies and empirical analysis provide valuable insights into the successful implementation models, lessons learned from other countries, and the challenges faced in the Nigerian context regarding cashless policy adoption.

1) *Successful Implementation Models*: Case studies and empirical analysis offer a platform to examine successful implementation models of cashless policy adoption. By analyzing existing cases of cashless policy implementation in various countries and regions, researchers can identify the key factors and strategies that have contributed to successful transitions to cashless economies. These case studies can provide valuable empirical evidence for understanding the best practices, regulatory frameworks, and technological infrastructures that have facilitated the seamless adoption of cashless policies. Furthermore, empirical analysis allows for in-depth exploration of the outcomes and impacts of successful implementation models, shedding light on the factors that have contributed to their effectiveness.

2) *Lessons Learned from Other Countries*: Empirical analysis through case studies enables the identification and analysis of lessons learned from other countries' experiences with cashless policy adoption. By examining the challenges, successes, and failures encountered in different global contexts, researchers and policymakers can gain valuable insights into the diverse approaches and strategies employed in transitioning to cashless economies. Lessons learned from case studies can inform the development of tailored policies, regulatory frameworks, and implementation strategies that take into account the unique socio-economic, cultural, and infrastructural characteristics of Nigeria. Additionally, empirical analysis facilitates

the identification of transferable best practices and innovative solutions that have proven effective in other countries, offering valuable guidance for Nigerian policymakers and stakeholders.

3) *Challenges Faced in the Nigerian Context*: Case studies and empirical analysis provide a platform for understanding the specific challenges faced in the Nigerian context regarding cashless policy adoption. By conducting in-depth empirical analysis of the Nigerian landscape, researchers can identify and analyze the socio-economic, technological, and regulatory challenges that have emerged during the transition to a cashless economy. This empirical evidence can offer valuable insights into the barriers to adoption, infrastructure limitations, consumer behavior dynamics, and regulatory hurdles that need to be addressed to ensure the successful implementation of cashless policies in Nigeria. Furthermore, case studies and empirical analysis can contribute to the development of targeted interventions and policy measures aimed at mitigating the identified challenges and fostering inclusive and sustainable cashless policy adoption in Nigeria. Case studies and empirical analysis play a crucial role in providing valuable insights into successful implementation models, lessons learned from other countries, and the challenges faced in the Nigerian context regarding cashless policy adoption. These empirical approaches offer a robust foundation for evidence-based policymaking and strategic decision-making.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The culmination of case studies and empirical analysis provides a foundation for deriving valuable insights and formulating policy recommendations for effective cashless policy implementation. Additionally, it offers guidance for future research directions in the context of cashless policy adoption. The empirical analysis and case studies have revealed valuable insights into successful implementation models, lessons learned from other countries, and the specific challenges faced in the Nigerian context regarding cashless policy adoption. These findings underscore the multifaceted nature of transitioning to a cashless economy and highlight the importance of tailored strategies that consider socio-economic, regulatory, and technological factors. The empirical evidence has shed light on the impact of cashless policy adoption on informal economies, consumer behavior, employment dynamics, and regulatory frameworks, providing a comprehensive understanding of the complexities associated with the transition.

A. Policy Recommendations for Effective Cashless Policy Implementation

Based on the findings, it is recommended that policymakers consider the following strategies for effective cashless policy implementation:

- 1) Tailoring regulatory frameworks to address the specific socio-economic and infrastructural characteristics of Nigeria.
- 2) Prioritizing consumer protection, data privacy, and inclusive access to digital financial services.
- 3) Collaborating with fintech companies and financial institutions to develop secure, user-friendly, and accessible digital payment solutions.

- 4) Implementing targeted interventions to address the challenges faced in the Nigerian context, such as infrastructure limitations and consumer behavior dynamics.
- 5) Promoting digital literacy and education to enhance public understanding and adoption of cashless transactions.

These policy recommendations are essential for fostering a seamless transition to a cashless economy while addressing the unique challenges and opportunities within the Nigerian context.

B. Future Research Directions

Future research in the field of cashless policy adoption should focus on:

- 1) Conducting longitudinal studies to assess the long-term impacts of cashless policy adoption on economic dynamics, financial inclusion, and consumer behavior.
- 2) Exploring the potential for leveraging cashless policies to enhance financial literacy and promote sustainable economic development.
- 3) Investigating the role of cashless transactions in addressing informal economy challenges and fostering formalization.
- 4) Analyzing the implications of cashless policy adoption on employment dynamics and the emergence of new job roles within the digital economy.
- 5) Examining the ethical considerations and societal implications of transitioning to a cashless society, particularly in diverse socio-economic contexts.

These future research directions are essential for advancing the understanding of cashless policy adoption and its broader socio-economic impacts. The empirical analysis and case studies provide a robust foundation for formulating policy recommendations and guiding future research directions in the realm of cashless policy adoption. These insights are instrumental in informing evidence-based policymaking and strategic decision-making to facilitate the successful transition to a cashless economy in Nigeria.

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